

Need based transformation of courtyards in response to climate vulnerability: A case of Shakbaria, Koyra

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Abstract

Courtyards have been an inherent component of rural settlements, predominantly in flat plain countries like Bangladesh. The essentiality of the courtyard is shaped by the socio-cultural, spatial, and functional needs of the inhabitants. This indigenous phenomenon, developed over centuries, has become a regional identity. However, the climate vulnerability of the region has compelled inhabitants to adapt the spatial layout of their homesteads. Particularly in coastal settlements, climate change-induced extreme natural events have impacted the social, ecological, economic, and physical domains. The coastal region of Bangladesh is currently experiencing these extreme events in real time. As a result of this climate vulnerability, the traditional courtyard is now subject to transformation—transformations that are increasingly need-based, driven by the changing conditions and necessities of daily life. This study intends to analyze the socio-spatial impact of climate vulnerability in rural homesteads, particularly the transformation of rural courtyards and their changing socio-cultural role within these homesteads. The study employed a qualitative approach to analyze the morphological data of the selected homesteads in the study area. Data collection and analysis were carried out at both the settlement and dwelling unit levels. The study highlights the increasing functional use of rural courtyards and their diminishing identity as socio-cultural spaces. The transitional function was also found to be more channelized and directive rather than omnidirectional. These findings reflect changing rural spatial dynamics and highlight the need for climate-responsive design solutions.

Keywords: *Climate vulnerability, Rural homestead, Courtyard transformation, Coastal settlements, Socio-spatial impact.*

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is the seventh most disaster-prone and climate-vulnerable country in the world (Omi et al., 2025). In recent decades, there has been a substantial rise in the frequency and severity of climate change induced extreme events (Chowdhury et al., 2022). These events include sea level rise, cyclones, increased salinity, prolonged flooding, increased temperature and heat waves, drought, and greater rainfall variations. Such climate related extreme scenarios have become regular occurrences all over the world. In particular, the low elevation coastal zones are affected the most. People living in this zones are at risk from sea-level rise, stronger storms and other seaward hazards (McGranahan et al., 2007). Bangladesh has a 700 km stretched coastline, encompassing about 20% of the national land area, which constantly faces the colossal and widespread impacts of these natural hazards (Ahmad & Jhara, 1997). Especially, the rural areas within this zone are disproportionately affected due to their limited adaptive capacity (Omi et al., 2025). As a result, many people are forced to move out of their homes, abandoning land property and livelihood (Hossain et al., 2012). While some people have managed to relocate from the vulnerable areas, the people who remain in their homes are adhering to adapt to the dreadful circumstances (*Rising above Adversity*, 2020).

According to Haq (1992), human dwellings are man's reaction to natural forces. The physical and social realities of the surrounding environment reflect on the nature and form of dwelling spaces. In this context, adaptation and coping nature of coastal communities (Ahmad & Jhara, 1997) must reflect on their dwellings. In indigenous rural homesteads the central courtyard is the most prominent element of its unique architectural style (Faruk & Rashid, 2024). Over time indigenous courtyards have inherited an enormous amount of information about the inhabitants social, cultural, habitual, and livelihood (Shakil, 2022). Consequently, any spatial adaptation or transformation within these homesteads must reflect on the courtyard. Although several recent studies have addressed the formation and temporal transformation of indigenous courtyards, a substantial gap remains in understanding this transformation in the context of climate change and evolving needs of inhabitants in coastal communities.

Traditional homestead patterns have evolved in the low-lying alluvial floodplain land of Bangladesh over centuries (Hasan, 1985). The formation of a homestead starts with raising a mound with mud to separate an area

for the house from the surroundings (Haq, 1992). After raising the land, the main dwelling unit and ancillary structures such as the kitchen, cowshed, and granaries are built gradually around a central open space. Usually, a homestead consists of a number of closely spaced rectangular buildings with one to two rooms, each one single-story or occasionally double-story, arranged around a square or rectangular courtyard (Ahmed, 2012). Additionally, an adjacent veranda can be a part of the freestanding-built forms. After the primary formation, an incremental expansion and subdivision of the original house is common in traditional homesteads (Haq, 1992). With time the spatial requirement of a family increases as the family grows. More dwelling structures and ancillary structures are added around the courtyard and form new homesteads. Although the formation of a homestead around a courtyard in an organic manner can produce enormously diverse patterns, Hasan (1985) and Haq (1992) categorized the rural courtyards based on incremental growth and subdivision of a household. Ahmed (2012) also found four main types of courtyards in rural homesteads. According to their study, the primary type is the initial stage of a house form, which consists of a single dwelling unit usually with an outdoor kitchen adjacent to a rectangular space. However, this phase does not represent a courtyard typology but rather a primary stage of a courtyard. The second typology illustrates a much more complete version, in which the incremental development of the initial courtyard transforms into a much more elaborate setup with multiple surrounding ancillary structures. This typology is generally used by a single household. The third typology is formed by further development when the family grows and more dwelling units are added around the court. Usually in this case, more than one household shares the central space as a common courtyard. The fourth typology is the most elaborate type of courtyard, where interlocking courtyards with open passageways connect different households. This depicts the process of successive generations residing in the same place and the incremental development of a homestead into a neighborhood.

The central open space, or the courtyard, plays the cohesive role in merging the different freestanding structures into one homestead. Also, a courtyard has physical, functional, and cultural significance that is inherent from the climatic and livelihood pattern of the inhabitants (Shakil, 2022). According to Hanson (1999), the formation of domestic spaces in vernacular house forms is primarily influenced by the culture and belief system of the people. In traditional Muslim homesteads, the courtyard is the private inner domain for women (Ahmed, 2012). To maintain the Muslim religious norms, courtyards represent an introvert nature. In Hindu and tribal communities, the gender-specific utilization of space is less rigorous. In Hindu homesteads the courtyard houses the symbols of religious rituals (Ahmed, 2012). However, across the communities, the courtyard is simultaneously used as a social space where guests and neighbors are welcomed. Apart from the socio-cultural significance, functionally a rural courtyard is the center of domestic life. The majority of the domestic ancillary activity of the family is done in the courtyard (Faruk & Rashid, 2024). According to (Nilufar, 2004) courtyard as an efficient household workstation is an example of how human behavior produces various forms of spatial representation; comprehensively, those spaces define indigenous public spaces. Further, courtyards function as a space for harvesting in the prominently agrarian rural society. During the harvesting season families use courtyards for harvesting and drying crops.

Due to various social, ecological, spatial, and economic reasons, the rural landscape is going through significant transformation (Shakil, 2022). This shift is particularly evident in the coastal region, where the increasing climate vulnerability is putting enormous pressure on available farmlands. Which is forcing people to use the courtyard area for farming purposes, transforming it from its original socio-spatial utilization. However, planting around the traditional houses to define them from the larger surroundings has always been a part of a rural homesteads (Haq, 1992). Homestead vegetable cultivation is a long-standing tradition in the rural areas. It combines vegetable cultivation, livestock rearing, and sometimes fish farming in household pond (Akter et al., 2019). Traditionally such activities were confined to the immediate area around the houses or small piece of land next to their dwelling areas (Kulsum et al., 2019). Under the current circumstances the courtyard has been used for cultivation and other occupying purposes diminishing the core identity feature of rural courtyards. Even though the courtyard is always regarded as a necessary component of indigenous homesteads, the changing circumstances have made it a subject of need and priority. This study aims to investigate the transformation of rural courtyards and the underlying factors due to the changing needs of the inhabitants.

3. Methodology

The study employs a qualitative approach to explore the reasons behind the need-based transformation of domestic courtyard in coastal rural contexts. Morphological and empirical data of the study area were collected by mapping and key person interviews. The interviewees were selected randomly from the villagers. The Data collection and analysis were carried out at both the settlement and dwelling unit levels. A total of 41 homesteads were surveyed chronologically within the village to find out the spatial formation and transformed utilization of the courtyard. This approach involved physical surveys of the study area, observing daily activities, practices of the inhabitants, and the use of spaces. To complement the insights gathered from the community, perspectives from additional stakeholders, including government and non-government organizations, were interviewed, and

their perspective are incorporated in the discussion. From the survey data three typological patterns are synthesized based on the spatial organization, circulation, and occupied space proportion within the courtyards for further discussion and analysis.

4. Profile of the study Area

The study has been carried out in Shakbaria village of Uttar Bedhkashi union (the lowest administrative unit of Bangladesh). It is a union of Koyra Upazila (sub-district unit) of the Khulna District. Uttar Bedhkashi is one of the southernmost regions of Bangladesh and is located on the rare side of the Khulna division (*figure. 1a*). With a total area of 22.44 square kilometers, Uttar Bedhkashi is one of the seven unions of Koyra Upazila. The total population of the Uttar Bedhkashi union is 20,528, with 677 people living per square kilometer (Biswas et al., 2015). Besides, the union is only 20 km away from the Bay of Bengal. The Sundarbans mangrove is situated between the Bay of Bengal and the settlement. The study area falls within the coastal zone which exhibit three core geophysical characteristics that distinguish the coastal zone from other regions of the country: the dynamic interplay of tidal regimes, the prevalence of soil and water salinity, and the frequent occurrence of cyclones and storm surges (Parvin et al., 2016).

Figure 01. (a) Location of the study area within the map of Bangladesh and subsequently within the Khulna divisional map. (b) The study area in relation to surrounding unions and nearby rivers. (c) The study area showing adjacent villages and river networks. Source: Mapped by authors based on google satellite images.

In particular, the study area is a narrow connecting (*figure. 1b*) land between the two unions of Uttar Bedhkashi and Dakhin Bedhkashi. At its narrowest point the width of the land is less than 300 meters. Moreover, on the northern side of the connecting land there is another village, *Gabbunia* (*figure. 1c*). Surrounded by the two major rivers, the study area is flanked by two different embankments. The village is situated along the embankment adjacent to the Rai River. The embankment on the opposite side adjacent to the *Kopotakho* River is significantly more vulnerable, as the *Kopotakho* River is larger and its water pressure is much higher. Consequently, water breaches the embankment and floods the village during the natural calamities. Most of the people of the study area earn their livelihood by shrimp farming, fishing, livestock rearing, collection of resources from the forest, etc. Crop farming used to be one of the main economic activities. However, in the last few decades frequent saline water intrusion, tidal inundation, and erratic rainfall gradually forced the inhabitants to alter their livelihood (Roy et al., 2022). This study area was selected as it is one of the most affected areas by the impacts of climate change in Bangladesh and consists of the southernmost human settlements of Bangladesh. This part of the country often comes into focus due to facing extreme climate-induced natural events.

Figure 02. Masterplan of Shakbaria Village, Koyra, illustrating the spatial organization based on different types of courtyards.
Source: Authors

5. Findings and Discussion

Within the study area, a total of 41 homesteads were surveyed, and among the organic pattern of the courtyards, a three typological spatial pattern was synthesized to categorize the socio-spatial data for analysis. From the spatial evolution and organization, the courtyards are categorized into three main typologies. In this study the courtyards are categorized into three types. The first type is a single household around a distinct courtyard consisting of a main dwelling unit and other ancillary structures. The second type is the result of the development of the first type and the outcome of a family growth comprising two or more families sharing a common courtyard. And the third and final type is the most elaborate arrangement, in which interlocking courtyards link multiple households.

Though traditional open courtyards are generically used for circulation, the basic domestic functions, and harvesting. Therefore, courtyards were always kept open. But the changing scenarios in the coastal regions inhabitants have adapted to their needs; as a result, the primary attribute of openness of a courtyard is gradually diminishing. Inhabitants are occupying the central space for functional purposes. A significant number of households are using the courtyard for seasonal cultivation. Vegetables and fresh water plants are cultivated within the courtyard. The study found out that among the 41 homesteads surveyed, 24 grow different types of vegetables and freshwater plants within their courtyards. Moreover, inhabitants occupy a substantial percentage of the courtyard, which is unlike its archetypal use in indigenous homesteads. As a consequence, the central circulation space is channelized into specific linear circulation, and the spatial organization is changing. From the qualitative analysis in this context, three core scenarios can be depicted using the ideal courtyard patterns.

The first scenario (*Figure 3a*) includes the type of households that occupy up to 50% or less of the courtyard area for vegetable cultivation. In the single courtyard typology, fresh water plants and vegetables are planted around the courtyard. As the courtyard is comparatively smaller, usually cultivable space is acquired adjacent to ancillary buildings or the boundary wall. Although this makes the court smaller, the basic essence of openness is maintained. For the shared courtyard homestead, inhabitants mostly use the central part of the court maintaining the surrounding area as circulation. Other examples show the cultivable area is acquired close to a house form instead of being acquired centrally. In that case one house form is accessed laterally. For the interlocking courtyard type, at least one of the courts is used for cultivation. The position of acquiring the cultivable area within the courtyard may vary, but all the house forms have proper access, and the essence of a courtyard is maintained.

In the second scenario (*figure. 3b*) homesteads acquire more than 50% of the courtyard area. Generally, this type of homestead has a smaller courtyard area, and to cultivate it, inhabitants have to acquire a larger percentage of the courtyard area. In this scenario the access to different house forms is transformed from an omnidirectional central space to a channeled narrow path. Additionally, the archetypal identity and significance of a courtyard are merely perceivable. Particularly the social attribute is completely obliterated.

The third scenario (*figure. 3c*) most closely retains the identity of a courtyard and, at the same time acquires enough area for cultivation. As is this typology, the area for cultivation is acquired from the courtyard in segments, and the acquired area typically constitutes 20-30% of the total area. In this case mostly creeper plants are cultivated, and the pitch roofs are used for the surface to grow the plants. As smaller spaces are acquired the circulation and accessibility to different house forms are merely interrupted. Additionally, the central space stays open.

Figure 03. (a) Acquired cultivable land does not interfere with accessibility to the house forms; (b) Acquired cultivable land partially disrupts accessibility to the house forms; (c) Acquired cultivable land largely obstructs accessibility to the house forms. Source: Authors

On this account, the question arises of what led to this transition to occupy space in the courtyard for cultivation purposes. The previous discussion on this paper does emphasize the climate vulnerability of this region. The consistent disruption in physical, economic, and social domains has resulted in the form of spatial and social adaptation of archetypal courtyard spaces. In particular the followings are the causes behind this adaptation process;

- **Saltwater Intrusion**

Frequent occurrence of climate-induced natural calamities imposes enormous pressure on the surrounding embankment of these coastal settlements. And often the embankments are unable to prevent overflowing water. As a consequence, the settlements face saline water inundation at frequent intervals. The majority of crops that can be grown are freshwater plants, meaning they cannot thrive in salt water. As a consequence, residents are cultivating crops to meet household needs within the courtyard.

- **Shortage of cultivable land**

Cultivable lands were already limited in proportion to the large population. And year by year it's reducing because of erosion; soil is becoming barren, population growth, etc. Additionally, erratic rainfall and a shortage of cultivable water make the cultivation process difficult and unfavorable. Further, shrimp farming is taking the place of other agrarian crops. Overall, the scarcity of land is another reason behind using the court differently.

- **Ensuring food security**

Inhabitants try to earth-fill the entire courtyard or at least the central portion of it annually. This is primarily intended to slightly elevate the courtyard surface and protect it from inundation. As a result, the courtyard becomes the second highest elevation after the house plinth. This raised level not only helps prevent waterlogging but also provides a more favorable condition for plantation compared to the surrounding areas. Additionally, the surrounding built forms of the homestead provide a natural barrier against both water inundation and strong winds. This spatial arrangement creates a relatively secure microclimate for freshwater vegetation during any adverse climatic incident.

- **Economic Vulnerability**

Due to insufficient and uncertain livelihood opportunities, the inhabitants strive to utilize all the available resources they have. The courtyard space presents a viable opportunity for growing vegetables for self-consumption, which can help to reduce their household expenses. As a result, families try to utilize the courtyard space effectively.

Additionally, the elevated courtyard surface enhances drainage and reduces the risk of prolonged waterlogging, further supporting plant survival.

Figure 04: Current scenario of courtyard farming. Source: Authors

Traditionally, small scale cultivation and vegetable plants has always held a part of indigenous courtyard, and the inclusion of small gardens was not uncommon. However, this study finds that in the context of climate vulnerability, fresh water cultivation has become an essential and dominant feature of the courtyard. Rather than functioning primarily as a transitional or communal space, the courtyard has evolved into a vital zone for subsistence cultivation, reflecting a significant transition in its spatial and functional role within the homestead.

6. Conclusion

The study was conducted to identify socio-spatial impact of climate vulnerability on coastal indigenous homesteads. In particular, it explores how adaptive responses to climate vulnerabilities have transformed the archetypal spatial configuration of indigenous courtyard.

Bangladesh is one of the most climate vulnerable countries in the world. The action of the industrialized countries has impacted disproportionately on the low-lying floodplain counties like Bangladesh. Consistent and frequent occurrence of extreme natural events have profound impact on the coastal settlements. The complex socio-economical context further exacerbates the negative impacts. Despite of all these, the resilience and adaptive capacity of the inhabitants remain the most significant positive strengths in coping with the adversity. The study found that, the courtyard as an open central space is no longer the primary archetypal element in the coastal indigenous homesteads. Inhabitants now utilize the space according to their needs, particularly for small scale cultivation. Consequently, the traditional attribute of omnidirectional circulation is gradually diminishing, giving the way to more channelized and liner access pattern. Indigenous homesteads have evolved over hundreds of years, adapting continuously to the changing need of the inhabitants. The transformation of the courtyard in the coastal belt of Bangladesh stands as a significant example of this adaptive evolution as a consequence of climate change.

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